

RESEARCH ARTICLE

D-Band Channel Modeling in Data Centers and Industrial Environments

YUNQI FENG¹, (Student Member, IEEE), MAMOUN GUENACH^{2,3}, (Senior Member, IEEE), NAZAR MUHAMMAD IDREES², (Member, IEEE), CLAUDE DESSET², (Member, IEEE), DAVID PLETS¹, (Member, IEEE), WOUT JOSEPH¹, (Senior Member, IEEE), AND EMMERIC TANGHE¹, (Member, IEEE)

¹Department of Information Technology, IMEC, Ghent University, 9052 Ghent, Belgium

²IMEC, 3001 Leuven, Belgium

³Department of Telecommunications and Information Processing, Ghent University, 9000 Ghent, Belgium

Corresponding author: Yunqi Feng (yunqi.feng@ugent.be)

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ABSTRACT This paper presents D-band channel modeling campaigns for short-range line-of-sight (LOS) communications in representative data center and industrial environments. An accurate multipath estimation framework, exploiting measured antenna radiation patterns, is utilized to extract multipath components (MPCs) with 0.1° angular resolution for precise large- and small-scale channel characterization. In the data center, directional inter-rack communication links exhibit a high path loss exponent (PLE) of 2.39 and a low mean delay spread of 1.32 ns, with cable obstructions increasing the PLE to 3.24 but further decreasing the mean delay spread to 0.59 ns. The omnidirectional measurement in the data center shows significant clustering effects in spatial-temporal domain. In contrast, industrial machine-to-machine (M2M) communication links, characterized through omnidirectional measurements, exhibit a lower PLE of 1.67. Mean values for delay spread, angular spread, and K-factor in industrial environments are moderate, which are 4.35 ns, 16.46° , and 8.11 dB, respectively, with weak clustering effects. The measurement results are compared and discussed with the literature across different environments and frequency bands for an overall understanding of unique propagation characteristics in these two environments. The quantitative measurement results contribute to D-band channel standardization.

INDEX TERMS D-band channel model, channel measurements, data center, factory, industrial environments.

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand for high throughput, ubiquitous connectivity, and ultra-low latency is driving the evolution of future wireless communication systems. The sub-terahertz (THz) spectrum, spanning from 100 GHz to 300 GHz, is a key enabler due to its vast available bandwidth. Within this range, D-band frequencies (110-170 GHz) are particularly promising for indoor short-range applications such as machine-to-machine (M2M) communications, smart factories, video streaming, and virtual reality [1].

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A thorough understanding of D-band radio propagation channels based on measurement data is essential for advancing wireless communication technologies and ensuring their effective deployment. Extensive D-band channel measurements have been conducted in indoor office and conference rooms [2], [3], [4] or outdoor environments [5], while measurement data from data centers and industrial environments are less reported. A comparative summary of existing D-band channel measurements across different environments is presented in Table 1. Industrial environments are typically characterized by heavy clutters and strong scattering in lower frequency bands [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], resulting in increased delay spreads (DS), angular spreads (AS), and a higher number of multipath components (MPCs).

TABLE 1. A comparative summary of existing D-band channel measurements across different environments.

References	Environment	Frequency [GHz]	Characterization of channel parameters	Measurement range
[2], [4]	Indoor office/conference room	140	LSP	Short
[3]		142	LSP and SSP	Wide
[5]	Outdoor microcell	142	LSP	Wide
[11]–[14]	Factory building	142	LSP and SSP	Wide
[15]		132		Medium
[17]	Data center	140	LSP and SSP	Medium

LSP: large-scale channel parameters, SSP: small-scale channel parameters

Recent studies on sub-THz industrial propagation confirm these trends and also report unique large-scale channel parameters (LSPs) [11], [12], [13]. Path loss (PL) analysis showed that the path loss exponent (PLE) ranged from 1.8 for line-of-sight (LOS) omnidirectional co-polarized links to 6.17 for non-line-of-sight (NLOS) directional cross-polarized links. Measured root mean square (RMS) delay spreads reached up to 66.0 ns, while RMS angular spreads could be as high as 103.7° [11]. A cross-polarization discrimination (XPD) of 27.7 dB further showed favorable conditions for polarization diversity [12]. Based on these measurements, a statistical channel model using the time cluster spatial lobe (TCSL) approach was developed in [14]. Additionally, multifrequency channel characterization from 28 to 220 GHz in industrial scenarios [15] indicated the frequency dependence of most LSPs. Although previous studies have covered wide measurement ranges, practical applications such as smart factories [16] typically involve short-range M2M communications, highlighting the need to investigate sub-THz industrial propagation over shorter distances in relevant environments.

The rapid growth of cloud services is driving an ever-increasing demand for data processing and storage. Traditional wired data centers rely on optical fibers, which offer high capacity but suffer from limited reconfigurability and hinder flexible network management. In contrast, wireless data center networks that integrate THz wireless links between racks present a promising alternative, delivering data rates comparable to fiber while enhancing flexibility. Early work on THz channel modeling in data center environments focused on the 300 GHz band, where practical LOS, NLOS, and obstructed-line-of-sight (OLOS) links were established using typical data center components such as cables and server rack frames [18], [19] to characterize path loss (PL) and root mean square delay spread (RMSDS) over short ranges. Cable-obstructed links experienced an additional 5–10 dB loss, while reflections from metal rack frames incurred a loss of 12.6 dB [18]. Delay-domain clusters were also identified. Extended measurements up to 12.5 m were reported in [20], categorizing links into medium-height, top-of-rack, and intra-rack types. Medium-height links were treated as omnidirectional with full angular information, whereas top-of-rack and intra-rack links were considered directional with well-aligned LOS or reflection components. However, research on D-band data center channel characterization remains scarce. The measurement

campaigns presented in [17] aimed to characterize D-band propagation channel parameters in data centers, but unique characteristics such as the impact of cable obstructions and rack reflections were not thoroughly investigated.

While D-band channel measurements in data centers and industrial environments are limited, a comprehensive comparison of channel measurement results across different environments and frequency bands is essential for a holistic understanding of propagation characteristics in millimeter-wave (mmWave) and sub-THz bands for various use cases. To address these research gaps, this paper presents D-band channel measurement campaigns in data centers and industrial environments. The main contributions are as follows:

- Large-scale D-band channel parameters are reported for short-range scenarios relevant to practical use cases in data centers and industrial environments. An improved MPC estimation algorithm, leveraging measured directional antenna patterns, enables extraction of MPCs with high angular resolution (0.1°).
- Clustering effects are evaluated for both D-band short-range channel measurements in data centers and industrial environments. Small-scale channel characterization is performed for data center measurements due to pronounced clustering effects, while clustering effects in industrial environments are found to be weak.
- A comprehensive comparison of channel measurement results across different environments and frequency bands is presented, providing an overall understanding of D-band propagation characteristics in data centers and industrial environments.

The paper is organized as follows. Channel measurement campaigns, including the setup, scenarios, and procedures, are introduced in Section II. Multipath estimation procedures to process the measurements are described in Section III. The measurement results from data centers and industrial environments are presented, discussed and compared with literature in Sections IV for large- and small-scale channel characterization in D-band. Conclusions are drawn in Section V.

II. CHANNEL MEASUREMENT CAMPAIGN

A. MEASUREMENT SETUP

The D-band channel sounding setup, which is illustrated in Fig. 1, characterizes the frequency-domain channel transfer function (CTF) using a two-port vector network analyzer

FIGURE 1. D-band radio channel sounding setup.

(VNA) (R&S ZVA67). The VNA generates a radio frequency (RF) signal in the 10.833-12.5 GHz range, which is upconverted to 130-150 GHz via a $\times 12$ frequency multiplier in the Tx frequency extender (VDI WR6.5VNATxRxM-5M). A synchronized external signal generator (R&S SMA100B) provides local oscillator (LO) signals from 10.810 to 12.477 GHz, which are also multiplied by 12 for mixing within the Tx and Rx extenders. The resulting intermediate frequency (IF) signals (IF_r and IF_t) are 276 MHz and fed into the VNA. Finally, the frequency domain CTF is measured as the ratio between the IF_r and IF_t . Measurement automation is facilitated through a personal computer (PC) connected to the VNA via the local area network (LAN).

The channel sounder parameter settings are detailed in Table 2. Prior to each measurement, a normalized through-calibration compensates for cable and connector losses, as well as phase variations. To safeguard the sensitive receiver, a 42 dB D-band attenuator with high phase stability is employed during the calibration and removed thereafter, with its attenuation accounted for in post-processing. The VNA performs frequency sweeps over a 20 GHz bandwidth, centered at 140 GHz, with a resolution bandwidth (RBW) of 100 Hz to suppress the noise floor. The Tx and Rx antennas are maintained at identical heights during measurements. This configuration yields a delay resolution of 50 ps (corresponding to a spatial resolution of 1.5 cm) and a maximum measurable delay of 100 ns, supporting path length evaluations up to 30 m. The dynamic range of the system enables path loss measurements up to 125 dB. Characteristics of the antenna used in the measurements are presented in Table 2 as well.

B. MEASUREMENT SCENARIOS

The data center environment is located in a server room in the data center of Ghent University. There are two hot aisles with many server racks in one server room. Between the two hot aisles, there is a cold aisle allowing cooling air from the air conditioning systems to flow into the servers. There are sliding doors made of glass at the entrance of the hot aisle, and the top of the hot aisle is also made of glass. The server

TABLE 2. Parameter settings for the D-band radio channel sounder.

Parameter	Values	
Frequency band	130-150 GHz	
Bandwidth	20 GHz	
Time resolution	0.05 ns	
Sampling points	2001	
Sampling interval	10 MHz	
Maximum delay	100 ns	
RBW	100 Hz	
Tx output power	13.8 dBm	
Omnidirectional antenna	Gain	3.3 dBi
	Vertical HPBW	45°
Directional antenna	Gain	23 dBi
	Horizontal HPBW	11.4°
	Vertical HPBW	9.6°
Rx azimuth rotation range	0-360°	
Rx azimuth rotation step	1°, 2°, 3°, 12°	

racks and the bottom end of the aisle are made of steel. The hot aisle and the server racks are shown in Fig. 2 (a).

Channel measurements in the data center environment are conducted within one of the two hot aisles, given their similar deployment. Within a hot aisle, there are two parallel rows of server racks separated by a central corridor. Each row contains twelve server racks which provide abundant metal reflective surfaces in the environment. Each rack has a dimension of 0.75 m in width, 1.2 m in depth, and 1.99 m in height. The central corridor has a dimension of 1.12 m in width, 11.24 m in length, and 2.10 m in height.

The industrial environments are located on the ground floor of a factory-like laboratory with a dimension of $21.3 \times 77.2 \times 12.2 \text{ m}^3$ for concrete research of Ghent University. An overhead view is shown in Fig. 2 (b). There are many machines and materials with different structures in the laboratory. The environment is characterized by a poured concrete floor and sparsely placed clutters consisting of different metals. The noise and dust generated by the operating machines effectively replicate the conditions of realistic industrial environments.

C. MEASUREMENT PROCEDURES

Channel measurements are classified as omnidirectional and directional measurements. In omnidirectional measurements, a vertically polarized omnidirectional antenna (type Mi-Wave 267D-387) [21] is used on the Tx side and a vertically polarized pyramidal horn antenna (type QuinStar QWH-D) is used on the Rx side. When measuring the angle of arrival (AOA), the horn antenna is fixed and rotated according to certain step size in horizontal plane to sample spatial profiles [22]. Unlike previous work that set the rotation step size around the measured -3 dB half-power beamwidth (HPBW) in the horizontal plane [23], we adopt different rotation step sizes from 1 to 12° for a denser spatial sampling, which can provide more measurements for MPC estimation procedures detailed in section III, and the robustness and reliability of the estimation results can thus be enhanced [24]. The synthesized omnidirectional channel model is a superposition

FIGURE 2. Photos and top-down floor plans of D-band channel measurements in the data center and industrial environments. (a) The server room in the data center environment. (b) An overhead view of the industrial environment. (c) The floor plan in the data center. (d) The floor plan of industrial site 1. (e) The floor plan of industrial site 2. (f) The floor plan of industrial site 3.

of the measured CTFs from all the spatial snapshots, i.e., measurements from all the Rx steering angles. In directional measurements, pyramidal horn antennas are used at both the Tx and Rx sides for point-to-point (P2P) transmission. Since they are pointing towards each other at the boresight, no angular information is available. All antennas used in the measurements are fed by WR6.5 waveguides and connected to frequency extenders.

Both directional and omnidirectional measurements are conducted in the data center. In the hot aisle of the data center, channel measurements are performed for six directional links and one omnidirectional link, with the floor plan illustrated in Fig. 2 (c). Directional P2P links are more of interest in the data center environment considering the use cases of rack-to-rack beam steering [20].

The Tx position remains fixed during the measurements while the Rx positions are changed as shown in Fig. 2(c). The measurement setup of one directional link in the data center is shown in Fig. 3 (a). The Tx and Rx are strategically placed near different rack front panels, so the six directional links are classified as inter-rack links and the omnidirectional link is classified as medium-height links [20]. For directional links, measurement distances range from 1 m to 6 m. Tx and Rx are at the same height of 0.9 m. LOS paths are guaranteed in the measurements. Ethernet cable clusters consisting of three cables are deployed near both the Tx and Rx sides for OLOS channel measurements. By rotating the Rx extender 90°, its polarization is switched to horizontal, thus cross-polarized channels are measured [25]. For the

omnidirectional measurement, the distance between Tx and Rx is 1.38 m which is quite short. The Tx and Rx are at the same height of 1.7 m in the omnidirectional measurement.

In industrial environments, three distinct measurement sites near operational machines are selected, as illustrated in the photos and floor plans in Fig. 2 (d)-(f). The measurement setup of one omnidirectional link in industrial environments is shown in Fig. 3 (b). Tx and Rx are placed near the machine edges to emulate realistic scenarios of M2M communications. There are nine omnidirectional links at these three sites consisting of six LOS links and three OLOS links, in which obstruction is caused by shadowing of machine parts. Omnidirectional links are more of interest

FIGURE 3. Measurement setups for (a) directional channel measurements in the data center with cable obstruction. (b) omnidirectional channel measurements in industrial environments with machine edge obstruction.

in industrial environments to guarantee reliable and robust industrial control, in which MPC information is useful. The distances of the measured links range from 1 m to 5 m. The Tx and Rx are all at the same height of 1.6 m in these measured links.

III. MULTIPATH ESTIMATION PROCEDURES

In this section, mathematical modeling of the D-band channel measurements and the data post-processing procedures are presented, in which spatial-temporal multipath components are estimated from initial frequency-domain channel measurements for large- and small-scale channel characterization in D-band.

A. MULTIPATH CHANNEL MODEL

In the measurements, the Tx antenna is fixed while the Rx antenna can steer to different directions. Each frequency-domain CTF measured by the VNA at a certain Rx steering angle is a sum of all the multipath power from a certain Rx steering angle, and the mathematical modeling in the linear scale is [26]

$$H(f_n, \Theta_{R^{th}}) = \sum_{l=1}^L \alpha_l \cdot G_t(\Theta_{r,l}) \cdot G_r(\Theta_{t,l}) \times e^{-j2\pi f_n \tau_l} + W \quad (1)$$

in which f_n represents the n^{th} frequency point, and there are N frequency points. $\Theta_{R^{th}}$ includes all the angular information contained at the R^{th} steering angles consisting of angle-of-departure (AOD) information $\Theta_{t,l}$ and AOA information $\Theta_{r,l}$ of the l^{th} path. L is the number of detectable paths, α_l is the complex path gain of the l^{th} path consisting of both amplitude and phase responses, $G_t(\Theta_{t,l})$ and $G_r(\Theta_{r,l})$ are the complex radiation patterns with both amplitude and phase responses of the Tx and the Rx antenna at different steering angle, $e^{-j2\pi f_n \tau_l}$ represents the phase shift caused by the time-of-arrival (TOA) τ_l of the l^{th} path, and W is the measurement noise. (1) is a straightforward representation of a single element in the vector form directional CTF $H_{dir}(\Theta_{R^{th}}) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$. Since there is only one spatial snapshot, angular information is not available in $H_{dir}(\Theta_{R^{th}})$. While the omnidirectional CTF $H_{omni}(\Theta_r)$ is synthesized with $H_{dir}(\Theta_{R^{th}})$ from all the Rx steering angles to a matrix form

$$H_{omni}(\Theta_r) = [H_{dir}(\Theta_1), \dots, H_{dir}(\Theta_R)] \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times R} \quad (2)$$

in which R is the total number of Rx steering angles and Θ_r contains the full angular information from all the Rx steering angles. Both (1) and (2) include the influences from antennas, and they should be removed in post-processing for the purpose of channel modeling.

B. POWER DELAY PROFILE THRESHOLDING

Since (1) is the Fourier transform of the temporal CTF, to obtain the power delay profile (PDP), an inverse discrete Fourier transform (IDFT) should be applied to the frequency domain CTF $H(f_n, \Theta_{R^{th}})$ with a standard Hanning window

ω_{Hann} to suppress the side lobes and preserve the main lobe of the signal with a good balance

$$h(\tau_n, \Theta_{R^{th}}) = \text{IDFT}(2 \cdot \omega_{Hann} \cdot H(f_n, \Theta_{R^{th}})) \quad (3)$$

in which τ_n represents the measurable delays in the unit of the time resolution in Table 2. A factor of 2 is multiplied to compensate for the coherent gain caused by the Hanning window, which is around 3 dB [27]. The PDP at the R^{th} steering angle in a vector form is

$$\text{PDP}_{R^{th}} = [|h(\tau_1, \Theta_{R^{th}})|^2, \dots, |h(\tau_N, \Theta_{R^{th}})|^2]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1} \quad (4)$$

Similarly, the directional PDP is exactly expressed by (4). In omnidirectional measurements, to visualize the power as a function of both delay and angle, the PDPs from all steering angles are combined to form the power delay angular profile (PDAP) in a matrix form

$$\text{PDAP} = [\text{PDP}_1, \dots, \text{PDP}_R] \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times R} \quad (5)$$

The PDPs of the directional and omnidirectional measurements from single Rx steering angles before denoising are shown in Fig. 4 (a) and (b), respectively. The noise threshold P_n is estimated to be -80 dBm for directional measurements and -100 dBm for omnidirectional measurements, which are 20 dB above the mean noise floors in these two types of measurement setups [28]. The difference in noise thresholds between directional and omnidirectional measurements arises from the distinct antennas used at the Tx side.

To denoise the measurements, a threshold P_{th} is applied to each measured PDP, representing the maximum allowable difference between the powers of a certain path and the strongest path in the channel [20] and a P_{th} of -40 dB is applied. The final denoising threshold P_t is set to the maximum of P_n and P_{th} .

Fig. 4 (a) and (b) present the PDPs from directional measurements and spatial snapshots in omnidirectional measurements respectively. It can be seen that directional PDPs are more dominated by LOS components than omnidirectional PDPs. The denoised PDPs from all spatial snapshots in an omnidirectional measurement are then used to form the PDAP in (5).

FIGURE 4. Power delay profiles before denoising for (a) directional and (b) omnidirectional links.

C. SPATIAL LOBE PROCESSING

In omnidirectional measurements, after denoising the PDPs, the power angular profile (PAP) is obtained in a vector form by summing the matrix elements in (5) along the column dimension as

$$\text{PAP} = \left[\sum_{n=1}^N |h(\tau_n, \Theta_1)|^2, \dots, \sum_{n=1}^N |h(\tau_n, \Theta_R)|^2 \right] \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times R} \quad (6)$$

Without the summation across the delay bins, the PAP can also be determined for each delay bin, which covers 0.05 ns in our setup

$$\text{PAP}_n = \left[|h(\tau_n, \Theta_1)|^2, \dots, |h(\tau_n, \Theta_R)|^2 \right] \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times R} \quad (7)$$

When the Rx antenna is steered in different directions in omnidirectional measurements, it is possible that the same MPC is observed multiple times in adjacent pointing directions due to the radiation pattern of the directional antenna, especially the strong LOS component. The concept of the spatial lobe (SL) from [14] and [29] is adopted here to identify the dominant directions covering one or multiple consecutive steering angles.

The concept of SL is applied in our processing as follows. First, peaks are detected over ten consecutive delay bins in each measured PDP to eliminate ghost paths. This approach relies on finite sampling points in the inverse Fourier transform and the practical assumption that only one path exists within a 0.5 ns interval at a given Rx steering direction. The remaining components within the detection range are merged with the detected peak and then set to the temporal noise floor of -120 dBm in omnidirectional measurements. Second, a synthesized PDP is generated by summing up processed PDPs from the first step, and a second peak detection procedure is performed on the synthesized PDP over five consecutive delay bins to eliminate possible Rx position drifts in different snapshots which can variate delay information of the same measured MPC. Afterwards, a synthesized PDAP is formed using the PDPs after peak detections according to (5). PAPs under each delay bin that exhibit power above the noise floor are extracted and separated as SLs. Similar to the PDP denoising steps, a spatial threshold of -20 dB which limits the maximum difference between the powers of a certain path and the strongest path within an SL can be applied. The noise threshold is set to -100 dBm which is the same as the noise threshold in PDP denoising, and the final denoising threshold is chosen as the maximum of the two thresholds.

Two extracted and processed SLs are shown in Fig. 5 (a) and (b). One and two directions can be observed in the presented SLs, respectively. The SL application does not omit arrival directions with weaker powers, but refines the measurement results because these directions are typically scanned multiple times during the measurement procedure, so the strongest measurement of an MPC is retained in the

FIGURE 5. Spatial lobes observed from (a) industrial site 2 at a distance of 1.575 m under the delay of 5.3 ns. (b) industrial site 3 at a distance of 1.7 m under the delay of 11.85 ns.

spatial domain. PDPs under the identified SLs are extracted to form a refined lobe-wise PDP.

D. SPATIAL-TEMPORAL MULTIPATH COMPONENTS EXTRACTION

In the refined PDP after the spatial lobe processing, each temporal component corresponds to one or multiple steering angles within a spatial lobe, but they are supposed to come from one MPC direction. By setting a high spatial threshold when processing the SLs, such angular uncertainty can be relieved or even eliminated, but such method is not adopted, the reason is twofold: i) the angular resolution for MPC estimation is then only determined by the step size of pointing angles, which results in inaccurate directional antenna pattern de-embedding at Rx side. ii) a considerable amount of delay components under the same arriving angle can be discarded erroneously, which can cause severe inaccuracy in MPC estimation.

Consequently, we preserve multiple measurements to estimate the angle of each MPC. Following the antenna de-embedded multipath extraction (ADME) algorithm in [14], the true MPC power, denoted by P_{tr} for the detected path is weighted by the antenna gain in the true AOA direction, which usually does not align exactly with the pointing angles

$$P_{tr} = \frac{P_r}{G_t G_r(\Theta_{tr})} \quad (8)$$

in which P_r is the received power, G_t is the known omnidirectional antenna gain at Tx side, and $G_r(\Theta_{tr})$ is the Rx antenna gain at the true AOA direction Θ_{tr} , which is assumed to be within the range of the detected SL Ω_{SL} . By applying the directional antenna pattern as weights to different pointing angles in the SL with a step size of the antenna pattern granularity, observations of the true MPC power are produced. The element in each observation is expressed by (8) with different testing angles $\tilde{\Theta}_{tr}$. Since noise statistics are not available, the true MPC power \tilde{P}_{tr} is

estimated as the mean of each observation

$$\tilde{P}_{tr} = \frac{1}{P} \sum_{\tilde{\Theta}_{tr} \in \Omega_{SL}} \frac{P_r(\tilde{\Theta}_{tr})}{G_t G_r(\tilde{\Theta}_{tr})} \quad (9)$$

in which P is the number of elements in one observation, i.e., number of temporal paths in an SL. According to the minimum mean squared error (MMSE) criterion, the best angle estimation $\hat{\Theta}_{tr}$ is the one that produces smallest variance for the set of power estimations, i.e., minimum estimation error

$$\hat{\Theta}_{tr} = \arg \min_{\tilde{\Theta}_{tr}} \text{Var} \left(\frac{\tilde{P}_{tr}}{G_t G_r(\tilde{\Theta}_{tr})} \right) \quad (10)$$

and the MPC power estimation \hat{P}_{tr} is determined accordingly by substituting $\hat{\Theta}_{tr}$ into (9). The estimated angles and MPC powers are assigned to the detected paths in the refined PDP as the final spatial-temporal MPC extraction results.

The angular resolution is therefore determined by the granularity of the antenna pattern rather than the Rx steering angle. However, the robustness and reliability of the estimation can be enhanced by having more spatial snapshots, i.e., smaller rotation step sizes, which is a practical law in estimation theory [24]. We obtain the detailed H-plane (horizontal) and E-plane (vertical) radiation patterns of the horn antenna at 140 GHz with a granularity of 0.1° from the manufacturer QuinStar as shown in Fig. 6. Therefore, we have a finer angular resolution than in [14] for azimuth angle estimation. Since the Rx and Tx are at the same height, and the vertical beamwidth of the horn antenna is narrow, most propagation components are concentrated in the horizontal plane. After antenna de-embedding, the final spatial-temporal MPCs can be constructed for channel characterization.

FIGURE 6. D-band pyramidal horn antenna radiation patterns in H-plane (horizontal) and E-plane (vertical) measured at 140 GHz provided by the manufacturer QuinStar.

Considering typical receiver sensitivity of 40 dB, extracted MPC results in industrial and data center environments after the antenna pattern de-embedding are shown in Fig. 7. It can be observed from the figures that LOS paths predominantly appear around 0° . Clustering effects are more pronounced in the data center environment than the industrial environment by visual inspection. The reason is two fold: i) although the measurements in two indoor environments are all conducted in a short range, the data center environment is more compact and corridor-like, which can produce more scattering bounces

while the industrial environments are relatively open with more deterministic clutters. ii) the material encountered in the data center is mostly steel which is shown to contribute more reflections [4], while material compositions in the industrial environments are more diverse.

FIGURE 7. Spatial-temporal MPC extraction results under a 40 dB receiver sensitivity from (a) industrial environments. (b) the data center.

E. SMALL-SCALE CHANNEL CHARACTERIZATION

As shown in Fig. 7 (a), clustering effects are weak in our measured industrial environments, which is a contrast to the work in [15], in which longer measurement ranges up to 12 m are covered. Since the measurement range is short in our measurement, the major clutters in the environment are more deterministic, and their propagation contribution can be easily separated with less stochastic characteristics. Although clustering algorithms such as K-means [30] can exploit such prior environmental knowledge, some discrete components shown in Fig. 7 (a) are potential outliers and can be misclassified into the main clusters. Therefore, we do not perform small-scale channel characterization on omnidirectional measurements from industrial environments.

However, in contrast, clustering effects of the omnidirectional measurement from the data center environment are quite pronounced as shown in Fig. 7 (b) due to its structure and material characteristics despite a short measurement range. Thus, to evaluate the clustering characteristics in data center environments, density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise (DBSCAN) algorithm is adopted [31]. It groups data points into clusters based on the local density of neighboring points, identifying core points and marking those do not meet the density criteria as noise. It is effective for discovering clusters of arbitrary shapes but is subject to the choice of two hyper parameters, one is the minimum number of points in a cluster, and the other is the maximum distance between two elements within the same cluster, which is commonly evaluated using the metric of multipath component distance (MCD) [28] in small-scale channel characterization

$$\text{MCD}_{ij} = \sqrt{\|\text{MCD}_{\phi,ij}\|^2 + \xi \|\text{MCD}_{\tau,ij}\|^2} \quad (11)$$

in which ξ is a delay scaling factor to balance the delay and angle resolution in the clustering algorithm, and MCD_{ij} is the MCD between the i^{th} and the j^{th} path consisting of the

TABLE 3. A summary of our modeled D-band radio channel parameters and their comparison with literature.

Scenario	Data center environments						Industrial environments				Indoor office room	3GPP indoor	3GPP factory	
	Our work		[17]		[20]		Our work		[15]		[32]	[33]		
References	130-150		130-140		300-308		130-150		129-135	26-30	130-143	140		
Propagation condition	Dir LOS	Dir OLOS	Omni LOS	Dir LOS	Omni LOS	Omni LOS	Omni LOS	Omni OLOS	Omni LOS	Omni LOS	Omni LOS	Omni LOS		
PLE	2.39	3.24	-	2.03-2.54	1.37-1.39	-	1.67	-	1.7-1.78	1.41-1.51	2.11	1.72	1.63	
XPD [dB]	36.17	26.13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11	12	
SF [dB]	μ	0.50	2.00	-	-0.04-0.70	0.08-1.56	-	-0.82	-	-	-	0	0	
	σ	1.18	4.23	-	2.82-4.05	1.79-4.96	-	1.45	-	1.11-3.06	1.39-2.25	3.29	3	4
RMSDS $\log_{10}(s)$	μ	-9.02	-9.38	-8.20	-	-8.03-8.22	-8.08	-8.39	-8.06	-8.36	-8.09	-8.39	-7.71	-7.32
	σ	0.53	0.53	-	-	0.14-0.24	0.18	0.27	0.21	0.26	0.33	0.27	0.18	0.15
RMSAS $\log_{10}(^\circ)$	μ	-	-	1.25	-	1.40-1.52	1.60	1.20	1.52	1.29	1.41	1.46	1.37	1.39
	σ	-	-	-	-	0.20	1.60	0.21	0.29	0.26	0.24	0.25	0.38	0.46
K [dB]	μ	23.75	20.26	8.98	-	5.71-7.59	8.15	8.11	0.55	13.29	11.07	12.93	7	7
	σ	4.16	3.43	-	-	3.84-8.21	5.13	1.46	4.24	-	-	-	4	8
Cluster number	-	-	11	-	9.42-11.33	-	-	-	-	6.15-8.4	11.38-11.6	1.97	15	25
CDS [ns]	-	-	0.08-2.61	-	1.63-1.65	-	-	-	-	0.79-0.97	0.91-2.28	0.34	-	-
CAS [°]	-	-	0.37-13.62	-	2.36-2.46	-	-	-	-	7.72-8.25	9.21-9.82	5.69	8	8
γ [ns]	-	-	21.78	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Λ [/ns]	-	-	0.13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

LOS: line-of-sight, OLOS: obstructed line-of-sight, dir: directional, omni: omnidirectional, PLE: path loss exponent, SF: shadow fading, XPD: cross polarization discrimination, RMSDS: root mean square delay spread, RMSAS: root mean square angular spread, K: Rician K-factor, CDS: intra-cluster delay spread, CAS: intra-cluster angular spread, γ : inter-cluster decay rate, Λ : inter-arrival rate of clusters

$MCD_{\phi,ij}$ in the angular domain

$$MCD_{\phi,ij} = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{(\sin(\phi_i) - \sin(\phi_j))^2 + (\cos(\phi_i) - \cos(\phi_j))^2} \quad (12)$$

in which $\phi_{i,j}$ are the azimuth AOAs of two estimated MPCs, and the $MCD_{\tau,ij}$ in the delay domain

$$MCD_{\tau,ij} = \frac{\tau_{std}}{(\Delta\tau_{max})^2} |\tau_i - \tau_j| \quad (13)$$

in which τ_i and τ_j are the delays of two estimated MPCs, τ_{std} is the standard deviation of the delays, and $\Delta\tau_{max} = \max(\tau_l) - \min(\tau_l)$.

IV. RESULTS OF D-BAND CHANNEL CHARACTERIZATION

This section presents the results of D-band channel characterization for rack-to-rack links in the data center covering distances up to 5.8 m, and M2M links in industrial environments covering distances up to 4.5 m. A comparative analysis with existing literature is provided. Our modeled D-band channel parameters for both data centers and industrial environments and their comparison with prior studies are summarized in Table 3.

A. PATH LOSS

Path loss (PL) is defined as the quantitative measure of the signal attenuation from Tx and Rx. The CTF measured after calibration consists of the PL and antenna gains, and the PL is usually expressed in decibel form

$$PL(f_n) \text{ dB} = H(f_n) \text{ dB} - G_t(f_n) \text{ dB} - G_r(f_n) \text{ dB} \quad (14)$$

angular representations in (1) is omitted here for a simpler representation. $H(f_n) \text{ dB}$ is usually calculated as the average over a certain bandwidth

$$H(f_n) \text{ dB} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{f=f_n - \frac{N}{2}\Delta f}^{f_n + \frac{N}{2}\Delta f} H(f) \right) \quad (15)$$

in which f_n is the center frequency, Δf is the frequency interval, and N is the number of frequency points. With the measured frequency domain response of the antennas used in the measurements, the PL can be easily calculated.

The PLE is the slope of the PL which characterizes how fast the signal power decays with distance. The closed-in (CI) model [34] is usually used for the fitting of the PLE n

$$PL_{CI}(d) = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{4\pi d_0 f_n}{c} \right) + 10n \log_{10} \left(\frac{d}{d_0} \right) + \chi_\sigma \quad (16)$$

in which the first term on the right side is the reference free space path loss (FSPL) at a distance of d_0 which is selected as 1 meter, and χ_σ is a shadow fading (SF) term which is assumed to follow log-normal distributions. It is calculated as the deviation between modeled PL in (16) and measured PL in (14).

For directional PL modeling, (15) is a reliable approach to directly calculate the PL in the frequency domain since there is only one spatial snapshot. However, the Rx antenna is steered to different directions in omnidirectional measurements, so the measured spatial profiles are overlapping, which makes the modeling approach in (15) less accurate for omnidirectional PL modeling. Instead, we establish the PL model by superimposing gains of all the paths from the MPC estimation framework in Section III-D as the omnidirectional path loss P_m

$$P_m = \sum_{l=1}^L P_{l,m} \quad (17)$$

and fit the omnidirectional PL model using the CI model. The SF in omnidirectional path loss analysis is calculated as the deviation between (16) and (17).

1) DATA CENTERS

The modeling of D-band directional PLs for co-polarized LOS and OLOS P2P links in the data center is shown in Fig. 8 (a). The fitted LOS PLE is 2.39 and the SF term χ_σ has a mean of 0.5 dB and a standard deviation of 1.18 dB. The PLE result falls into the peer measured LOS PLE value between 2.03 and 2.54 reported in D-band data center measurements in [17], while the standard deviation of the SF term is smaller than their reported value, possibly due to our shorter measurement ranges. The reason for a PLE higher than the theoretical free space PLE of 2 is threefold: i) frequent cooling winds ventilated from cold aisles into hot which add turbulence and variations on radio propagation. ii) although there are many reflective surfaces in the environment, they hardly contribute to path gains due to narrow antenna beamwidth in directional measurements. iii) an antenna misalignment error exists, which can not be removed from directional P2P measurements.

The cable obstructions in the vicinities of both the transmitter and the receiver brings additional loss from 2 dB to 10 dB and results in an increased PLE of 3.24 and SF term with a mean of 2.00 dB and a larger standard deviation of 4.23 dB. To overcome such underestimated PL, directional beamforming techniques are supposed to be used in the data center sub-THz wireless links.

2) INDUSTRIAL ENVIRONMENTS

The D-band omnidirectional LOS PL modeling is shown in Fig. 8 (b). The fitted LOS PLE is 1.67 and the SF term has a mean of -0.82 dB and a standard deviation of 1.45 dB. The LOS PLE is considerably lower with the theoretical free space PLE of 2 and is also slightly

FIGURE 8. Path loss modeling for (a) directional links in the data center and (b) omnidirectional links in the industrial environments.

lower than peer reported values from 1.70 to 1.85 in [13] and [15], but is consistent with the 3GPP factory channel model extended to 140 GHz. The reason for a low PLE of 1.67 is twofold: i) shorter measurement ranges allow us to detect more MPCs with powers within the dynamic range of the channel sounder, thus contributing to the overall path gain. ii) The clutters in the environment contribute significant multipath gains in omnidirectional measurements, even though they are not densely placed. The standard deviation of the measured SF term is consistent with literature values from 1.11 to 3.06 in [13] and [15]. PL modeling and shadow fading analysis for omnidirectional OLOS links in industrial environments are not applicable due to limited measurement links.

B. CROSS-POLARIZATION DISCRIMINATION

Cross-polarization discrimination (XPD) is the ratio between the co-polarized signal component P_{co} and the cross-polarized signal component P_{cx}

$$XPD = 10\log_{10} \left(\frac{P_{co}}{P_{cx}} \right) \quad (18)$$

The D-band XPD measurements are conducted in the directional P2P measurements in the data center. According to the XPD measurement procedures in [25], we obtain P_{co} and P_{cx} from the co-polarized and cross-polarized LOS path power respectively. The mean value of LOS XPD is 36.17 dB. This indicates high polarization isolation which is quite favorable for polarization diversity schemes in sub-THz wireless data center links. The mean OLOS XPD value is 26.13 dB, 10 dB smaller than LOS XPD which is owing to the de-polarization effects from the deployed cable obstructions.

Similar de-polarization phenomenon is observed in [11] and [13].

C. DELAY SPREAD

The root mean square delay spread (RMSDS) is used to quantify the time dispersion of the radio channel

$$RMSDS = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{\tau} P_r(\tau) \tau^2}{\sum_{\tau} P_r(\tau)} - \left(\frac{\sum_{\tau} P_r(\tau) \tau}{\sum_{\tau} P_r(\tau)}\right)^2} \quad (19)$$

in which $P_r(\tau)$ is the received power, τ is the delay. The RMSDS can be obtained from both directional and omnidirectional measurements.

1) DATA CENTERS

The results of measured directional RMSDS in the data center under four different propagation conditions, i.e., line-of-sight co-polarization (LOS+Co), obstructed line-of-sight co-polarization (OLOS+Co), line-of-sight cross-polarization (LOS+Cx), obstructed line-of-sight cross-polarization (OLOS+Cx), are presented in Fig. 9 (a) with the minimum, maximum and mean measured values.

The measured directional RMSDS are all lower than 5 ns with the mean value below 2 ns. The LOS co-polarized channels feature the largest measured directional RMSDS of 3.20 ns and the largest mean value of 1.32 ns, while the values are lower for the OLOS co-polarized channels, which is not intuitive. A possible reason is that the cable obstruction attenuated some reflected paths to below the noise floor, so that time dispersion in the OLOS PDP is relieved.

Such low time dispersion is favorable for sub-THz wireless system design.

The measured directional RMSDS values for cross-polarized channels are all very low and close to zero, because highly mismatched polarizations decrease the powers of most paths below the noise floor, only one or two paths can be detected with powers slightly higher than the noise floor and much lower than co-polarized channel powers. In such case, cross-polarized channels are almost eliminated.

In contrast, the measured omnidirectional RMSDS in the data center at a distance of 1.38 m features an RMSDS of 6.26 ns after the MPC estimation procedures in Section III. More multipath components are extracted in omnidirectional measurements, thus the RMSDS is increased. Our measured omnidirectional RMSDS value aligns with the reported range of 6.02 to 9.03 ns in [17] for D-band data center channel modeling, as well as the 1.95 to 11.50 ns range reported in [20] for 300 GHz channel modeling. This suggests that omnidirectional RMSDS values in data center environments above 100 GHz may exhibit weak frequency dependence.

2) INDUSTRIAL ENVIRONMENTS

The measured omnidirectional RMSDS results for LOS and OLOS links are presented in Fig. 9 (b). The values of LOS RMSDS are still lower than 10 ns with and fall in the range of peer measurements in [13], indicating the possibility of developing low-latency and reliable control links in sub-THz M2M communications. The RMSDS values for OLOS links are higher than LOS links, up to 12 ns, due to attenuated LOS power and additional multipath propagation contributed from

FIGURE 9. The box plots of (a) measured directional RMSDS for four different kinds of links in the data center environment. (b) measured omnidirectional RMSDS for LOS and OLOS links in the industrial environments. (c) measured directional K-factor for co-polarized LOS and OLOS links in the data center environment. (d) measured omnidirectional K-factor for LOS and OLOS links in the industrial environments.

the machine edges as can be seen from Fig. 3 (d) to (f) and Fig. 3 (b).

D. RICIAN K-FACTOR

The Rician K-factor (K) is a parameter to evaluate the richness of MPCs in radio channels which quantifies the power ratio between the LOS components and the NLOS components. It is mathematically defined as

$$K = 10\log_{10}\left(\frac{P_{\text{LOS}}}{P_{\text{NLOS}}}\right) \quad (20)$$

LOS components here are extracted using the peak detection and power merging methods introduced in Section III-C. A high K-factor indicates strong LOS dominance, leading to a sparser multipath structure, whereas a low K-factor implies a rich-scattering environment. Similar to RMSDS, the K-factor can also be obtained from both directional and omnidirectional measurements.

1) DATA CENTERS

The measured directional K factors under LOS and OLOS copolarized conditions from the data center are presented in Fig. 9 (c). The measured directional K-factors range from 14.61 to 27.50 dB, which is intuitive for directional measurements with high LOS dominance. The measured directional OLOS K-factors are slightly lower. This is caused by the attenuation on the LOS path of data center cable obstruction near the Tx and Rx as can be seen from Fig. 3 (a).

The measured omnidirectional K-factor in the data center at a distance of 1.38 m features a lower value of 8.98 dB owing to increased MPC richness in omnidirectional measurements. Our measured omnidirectional K-factor is slightly higher than the reported values of 5.71 to 7.59 dB in [17] of the work in D-band data center channel modeling, which is due to our short measurement range, but is consistent with the reported values from 1.01 to 17.90 dB in [20] of the work in 300 GHz channel modeling.

2) INDUSTRIAL ENVIRONMENTS

The measured omnidirectional K-factors for the LOS and OLOS links from the industrial environments are presented in Fig. 9 (d). The measured LOS K-factors range between 6.06 and 11.20 dB, which fall within the range of peer measurements from 4.50 to 21.17 in [15] and are consistent with the measurement setups in which the dominated LOS paths are guaranteed in our short range measurements. In contrast, the measured OLOS K-factors decrease drastically with a mean of 0.55 dB because the significant drop in the LOS power and drastic increase in the multipath power occur simultaneously.

E. ANGULAR SPREAD

Root mean square angular spread (RMSAS) expresses how much the received powers are dispersed in the angular

domain. It is defined as

$$\text{RMSAS} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{\theta} |e^{j\theta} - \mu_{\theta}|^2 P_r(\theta)}{\sum_{\theta} P_r(\theta)}} \quad (21)$$

in which $P_r(\theta)$ is the received power, θ is the angle in radian and the mean angle μ_{θ} is

$$\mu_{\theta} = \frac{\sum_{\theta} e^{j\theta} P_r(\theta)}{\sum_{\theta} P_r(\theta)} \quad (22)$$

a smaller RMSAS means less spatial scattering, so that the power can be more focused in the direction of beamforming. Distinguished with the RMSDS and K-factor, RMSAS only applies to omnidirectional measurements where spatial snapshots are available to determine angular values based on different spatial amplitudes.

1) DATA CENTERS

The measured RMSAS in the data center at a distance of 1.38 m is 17.58°, which is lower than the reported values of 25.1 to 33.1° in [17] of the work in D-band data center channel modeling, and is higher than the reported values from 4.0 to 16.0° in [20] of the work in 300 GHz channel modeling.

2) INDUSTRIAL ENVIRONMENTS

The measured LOS RMSAS values in industrial environments range from 10.68° to 29.42° with a mean value of 16.46°, which are within the range of peer measurements in [13] but span a narrower range, possibly due to the short measurement ranges and relatively open environments with more deterministic clutters in our measurement sites. In contrast, the OLOS RMSAS values range from 20.28° to 59.19°. Such change in RMSAS from LOS links to OLOS links is much more drastic than the RMSDS and K-factor, because RMSAS is highly sensitive to signal dispersion in the spatial domain.

F. CORRELATION OF CHANNEL PARAMETERS

To analyze the inter dependencies among the D-band directional channel parameters, the Pearson correlation coefficients are evaluated

$$\rho = \frac{\sum_i [(X_i - \bar{X}) \cdot (Y_i - \bar{Y})]}{\sqrt{\sum_i (X_i - \bar{X})^2 \cdot \sum_i (Y_i - \bar{Y})^2}}, \quad (23)$$

in which X and Y are two sets of channel parameters with \bar{X} and \bar{Y} being their mean values.

1) DATA CENTERS

In Fig. 10 (a) and (b), the correlation coefficients among the measured D-band LOS and OLOS directional channel parameters in the data center environment are presented respectively.

For LOS channel parameters shown in Fig. 10 (a), strong negative correlations of -0.83 and -0.67 are observed between the K-factor and both the distance and the delay

FIGURE 10. Correlation coefficients among the distance, delay spread, shadow fading and K-factor from D-band directional measurements in the data center environments for LOS and OLOS copolarized channels.

spread respectively. Similarly, the shadow fading shows a strong positive correlation of 0.93 with the K-factor, indicating that in sparse environments with LOS dominance, large-scale power variations become more coherent with dominant signal paths. The delay spread and the distance exhibit a moderate positive correlation of 0.41, reflecting extended multipath components at greater ranges.

However, a different trend is revealed in OLOS scenarios. The correlation between the distance and the delay spread nearly vanishes with a small correlation coefficient of -0.04 , while the negative coefficient between distance and SF intensifies to -0.94 , suggesting that obstructions introduce more variability in large-scale fading in OLOS paths than LOS paths. The K-factor, while still negatively correlated with distance and positively correlated with SF, demonstrates a weaker dependency due to reduced LOS dominance. The correlation trends in our findings for D-band channel model in the data center are consistent with the 3GPP standards for indoor channel models below 100 GHz [33].

2) INDUSTRIAL ENVIRONMENTS

The correlation coefficients among measured D-band omnidirectional channel parameters are presented in Fig. 11.

FIGURE 11. Correlation coefficients among the distance, delay spreads, angular spreads, shadow fading and Rician K-factors from omnidirectional measurements in the industrial environments.

Several significant correlations are observed. There are strong negative correlations between K and RMSAS (-0.84) and distance (-0.31), in which the negative correlations between K and RMSAS are consistent with 3GPP standards for indoor industrial channel models below 100 GHz where the correlation value is -0.5 [33]. Meanwhile, strong positive correlation on distance can be observed in RMSDS (0.64) and SF (0.61), and RMSDS and SF are also highly correlated with a coefficient of 0.96. This means that when the

distances become large, the dispersion in the power and delay domain can increase, which results in a larger SF term and RMSDS a but a smaller K-factor. Moderate positive correlations can also be observed between RMSAS and RMSDS, and between RMSAS and distance, which are all around 0.25. These diverse correlations among our measured omnidirectional D-band channel parameters are contrary to the 3GPP channel standards for industrial environments below 100 GHz, in which almost no correlations can be observed except the negative correlations between RMSDS and K , and RMSAS between K . Possible reasons could be that we did channel sounding experiments in the frequency domain, so scenarios for channel measurements are limited to static scenarios and lack randomness.

G. SMALL-SCALE CHANNEL CHARACTERIZATION

The DBSCAN clustering result for the D-band omnidirectional channel measurement in the data center environment at a distance of 1.38 m is presented in Fig. 12 based on a -40 dB threshold on the estimated path gain. The minimum points in a cluster is set to 3 which means all the valid clusters should have at least three sub-paths, and the maximum distance within a cluster is set to 0.1 along with the delay scaling factor ξ of 100 in (11).

FIGURE 12. DBSCAN clustering results from the data center omnidirectional measurement with eleven clusters detected.

The delay, angle, and path gain of the strongest sub-path within each detected cluster are also indicated. In addition to the number of clusters, small-scale channel parameters including intra-cluster delay spread (CDS), intra-cluster angular spread (CAS), inter-cluster decay rates, and inter-arrival rates of the clusters can also be determined. The CDS and CAS can be calculated by applying the general definitions of RMSDS in (19) and RMSAS in (21) within each detected cluster. The inter-cluster decay rate, which describes how the power of the clusters, which is the sum of all the MPC power within a cluster, diminishes over time. According to cluster-based channel models [35], the power of the l^{th} cluster P_l is modeled as

$$P_l = P_0 e^{-T_l/\gamma} \quad (24)$$

where P_0 is the power of the first arriving cluster, T_l is the time delay of the first MPC within the l^{th} cluster, and γ is the inter-cluster decay rate, which can be estimated using a least-squares regression. The inter-arrival rate of clusters Λ

quantifies how frequently clusters of multipath components arrive at the receiver. Let $\Delta T_l = T_{l+1} - T_l$ denote the time interval between consecutive clusters, Λ is then calculated as the reciprocal of the average ΔT_l .

As shown in Table 3, the CDS is from 0.08 to 2.61 ns, the intra-cluster AS is from 0.37 to 13.62°, the inter-cluster decay rate is 21.78 ns, and the inter-arrival rates of the clusters is 0.13/ns. Compared to the literature work from [17] in D-band data center channel measurements, our small-scale channel parameters feature a consistent number of clusters but wider range of the intra-cluster DS and AS, which can be explained by different measurement configurations, different measurement ranges and different clustering algorithm settings.

Cluster 1 clearly corresponds to the LOS cluster. As shown in Fig. 2(c), the Tx and Rx are positioned near one side of the aisle. The angle of arrival (AoA) is defined relative to the Rx boresight and measured clockwise from -180° to 180° . Thus, MPCs originating from the top racks near the Tx and Rx are expected to have positive angles, while those from the bottom racks should have negative angles. MPCs from the entrance are expected to have angles around 0° , while those from the bottom end of the aisle should have angles near 180° . Based on these assumptions, cluster 5 is likely to originate from the top racks; clusters 2, 3, 4 are from the bottom racks; cluster 6, 8 and 11 should from the entrance door; and clusters 9 and 10 are from the bottom end of the aisle. The silhouette score [36], which measures how well each data point lies within its cluster relative to other clusters, is adopted here to evaluate the clustering performance. The silhouette score of the above clustering result is 0.14 and lies in the acceptable range from 0 to 1.

H. STATISTICAL CHARACTERIZATION

From the standardization perspective, it is necessary to model the measured channel parameters and MPCs using statistical distributions [33]. Directional channel parameters depend on not only the channel parameters from the propagation environments but also the antenna pattern, which are separately modeled in channel standards, so statistical characterization is only applied to omnidirectional channel measurement results rather than directional channel measurements.

We first model the statistical distributions of the large-scale channel parameters, including delay spreads, angular spreads, K-factors and shadow fading terms from LOS omnidirectional measurements in industrial environments. Delay spreads and angular spreads are modeled by log-normal distributions, and K-factors and shadow fading terms are modeled by normal distributions, which are common hypotheses.

For hypothesis testing, Shapiro-Wilk (SW) and Anderson-Darling (AD) tests are applied. For the SW test, $p > 0.05$ indicates the data follows a normal distribution. The AD test provides an A^2 statistic that quantifies the discrepancy between empirical and theoretical distributions; values below critical thresholds at standard significance levels (5%) support normality. Apart from assessing normality, both

tests are applied to log-transformed data, i.e., RMSDS and RMSAS, to assess log-normality. Based on the returned p and A^2 values, normality or log-normality of the set of parameters is confirmed.

The goodness-of-fit of log-normal distributions on delay spreads and angular spreads and normal distributions on K-factors and shadow fading terms are presented in Table 4. Since the returned p values in the SW tests are all higher than 0.05 and the returned A^2 values do not exceed the 5% significance levels in the AD tests, hypothesized distributions fit well on the four channel parameters. The cumulative distribution functions (CDF) along with the fitted distributions for the four channel parameters are shown in Fig. 13, and the mean μ and standard deviation σ of the fitting can be found on Table 3. The statistics of our modeled large-scale channel parameters are quite consistent with literature sub-THz measurement results in [15] as discussed in previous sections.

TABLE 4. Goodness-of-fit of log-normal distributions on RMSDS, RMSAS, and normal distributions on K-factor and SF.

	RMSDS	RMSAS	K	SF
p value of SW Test	0.52	0.41	0.59	0.61
A^2 value of AD Test	0.29	0.39	0.28	0.24
5% level of AD Test	0.68			

FIGURE 13. Statistical fittings of omnidirectional (a) RMSDS, (b) RMSAS, (c) Rician K-factor, and (d) SF term from D-band channel measurements in industrial environments.

Statistical modeling of the delay distribution in data center environments was presented in Section IV-G, following the clustering analysis. Since cluster-based channel models are a prerequisite for delay distribution modeling [33], this analysis is not extended to industrial environments, where clustering effects are weak and do not support reliable delay-based statistical modeling of MPCs. In contrast, the angular distribution—relevant for direction-aware communication system design—can be analyzed independently of clustering.

Laplacian distributions are fitted to the angular profiles extracted from omnidirectional measurements in both

environments, with modeling results shown in Fig. 14 (a) and (b). The median μ and scale parameter b of the Laplacian distribution are indicated for each case. To assess the goodness-of-fit, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test is employed [37], which is well-suited for general statistical distribution modeling. A p -value greater than 0.05 indicates an adequate fit. The p -values for the Laplacian distribution modeling of angular profiles in the data center and industrial environments are 0.32 and 0.06, respectively, confirming the suitability of the Laplacian model in both cases.

FIGURE 14. Laplacian distribution fittings on the angular profiles from (a) the data center. (b) industrial environments.

I. COMPARISON ACROSS DIVERSE SCENARIOS AND FREQUENCY BANDS

Table 3 summarizes our D-band measurements in data centers and industrial environments, and compares them with literature at different frequency bands and environments, including extensions of the 3GPP indoor and factory channel models to 140 GHz for benchmarking.

For LOS omnidirectional channel parameters, frequency-dependent trends are evident: D-band generally exhibits lower RMSDS and RMSAS and higher Rician-K factors compared to 28 GHz, indicating reduced multipath richness and stronger specular components at higher frequencies.

Environmental and scenario dependence are also pronounced for D-band large-scale channel parameters. Office rooms exhibit the lowest RMSDS, while data centers show the highest due to their unique structure and materials. However, office rooms have higher RMSAS values than both data centers and industrial environments. The highest omnidirectional LOS PLE is observed in office rooms, while the lowest occurs in data centers. In our D-band short-range measurements, 11 clusters are detected in data centers, but none in industrial environments; literature reports 6-8 clusters depending on the setup.

Measurement configurations also influence propagation characteristics. The PLE is generally higher in directional setups than in omnidirectional setups, due to fewer detected paths and increased sensitivity to antenna misalignment.

Compared to the extended 3GPP model, D-band LOS omnidirectional delay spreads, angular spreads, and cluster numbers are generally lower, K-factors are higher, and measured PLEs across different indoor and factory environments in D-band also show significant variation. These findings indicate that the 3GPP model does not accurately capture

D-band propagation channel characteristics, highlighting the need for new channel standards above 100 GHz.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper provides a comprehensive characterization of D-band channels for short-range communications in data center and industrial environments, addressing practical use cases. Multipath components are accurately extracted by incorporating realistic antenna patterns, enabling precise large- and small-scale channel characterization. In the data center, directional measurements for rack-to-rack links yield a high LOS PLE of 2.39, a high XPD of 36.17 dB, and low RMSDS below 5 ns. Cable obstructions near the Tx and Rx increase the PLE to 3.24, while reducing both RMSDS and XPD. The omnidirectional link in the data center exhibits pronounced clustering effects in spatial-temporal domain. In industrial environments, omnidirectional LOS channels exhibit a lower PLE of 1.67, with moderate mean values for RMSDS (4.35 ns), RMSAS (16.46°), and the K-factor (8.11 dB). Clustering effects are weak for short-range M2M links. Comparative analysis with existing literature highlights the limitations of the 3GPP model for D-band channel characterization. These quantitative results support the development of D-band channel standards.

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YUNQI FENG (Student Member, IEEE) was born in Wuxi, China. He received the B.S. degree in telecommunication engineering from Nanjing Tech University, Nanjing, China, in 2021, and the M.S. degree in multimedia information technology from the City University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong, China, in 2022. He is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree in electrical engineering with Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium. His research interests include radio channel modeling, signal processing, and over-the-air testing, for millimeter-wave and massive MIMO systems.

MAMOUN GUENACH (Senior Member, IEEE) received the degree from EMI, Morocco, in 1995, and the Ph.D. degree from UCL, Belgium, in 2002. He was a Postdoctoral Researcher with Ghent University, from 2002 to 2006, where he has been a part-time Visiting Research Professor, since 2015. He was a member of Nokia Bell Laboratories Technical Staff, from 2006 to 2019. Since 2019, he has been with IMEC, Leuven, as a Research Scientist. His main research interests include coding, modulation, synchronization, and MIMO equalization for high-speed wired and wireless communication technologies.

NAZAR MUHAMMAD IDREES (Member, IEEE) received the M.Sc. degree in physics from the University of the Punjab, Pakistan, in 2002, the M.Sc. degree in telecommunications from Government College University, Lahore, Pakistan, in 2004, and the Ph.D. degree in communications engineering from Johannes Kepler University, Linz, Austria, in 2012. With a strong academic background, he has held multiple teaching and research positions across institutions. He began his career as a Lecturer with the Government College University, Lahore, from 2005 to 2008, later serving as an Assistant Professor from 2013 to 2014. He then joined COMSATS Institute of Information Technology, Sahiwal, from 2014 to 2018, followed by a Postdoctoral Fellowship with Zhejiang University, Hangzhou, China, from 2018 to 2022. Subsequently, he worked as an Assistant Professor with Namal University, Mianwali, Pakistan, from 2022 to 2023. Since 2023, he has been a Researcher with IMEC, Leuven, Belgium, contributing to cutting-edge advancements in wireless systems. He is currently a Researcher specializing in wireless communications and signal processing. His research expertise includes signal processing for wireless communication and sensing, mobile radio channel modelling, and synchronization in distributed systems.

CLAUDE DESSET (Member, IEEE) has been the Leader of the communication systems team with IMEC, Leuven, where he has been working, since 2001. His main expertise is on high-throughput wireless communication systems and signal processing, focusing on modelling and optimizing physical-layer performance and power consumption. He is especially targeting MIMO-OFDM systems and algorithms, error-correction coding, and the impact of hardware implementation constraints

and non-idealities. Besides a main focus on mm-wave communication systems, he also has a background in massive MIMO and mm-wave radar systems.

WOUT JOSEPH (Senior Member, IEEE) was born in Ostend, Belgium, in October 1977. He received the M.Sc. degree in electrical engineering and the Ph.D. degree from Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium, in July 2000 and March 2005, respectively. His Ph.D. work dealt with measuring and modeling of electromagnetic fields around base stations for mobile communications related to the health effects of exposure to electromagnetic radiation. From 2007 to 2012, he was a Postdoctoral Fellow with the FWO-V (Research Foundation—Flanders), Brussels, Belgium. Since October 2009, he has been a Professor in the domain of “experimental characterization of wireless communication systems.”

He has been a PI of IMEC, Ghent University, since 2017. His research interests include electromagnetic field exposure assessment, propagation for wireless communication systems, antennas and calibration. Furthermore, he specializes in wireless performance analysis and quality of experience.

DAVID PLETS (Member, IEEE) has been a member of the IMEC-WAVES Group, Department of Information Technology (INTEC), Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium, since 2006, where he has also been a Professor since 2016. His current research interests include localization techniques and the Internet of Things (IoT), for industrial, agricultural, and healthcare applications. He is also involved in the optimization of wireless communication networks.

EMMERIC TANGHE (Member, IEEE) was born in Tielt, Belgium, in August 1982. He received the M.Sc. and Ph.D. degrees in electrical engineering from Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium, in 2005 and 2011, respectively. From September 2005 to May 2011, he was a Research Assistant with the Department of Information Technology, Ghent University (imecUGent/INTEC). His scientific work focused on the modeling of indoor and outdoor propagation through field measurements.

Since May 2011, he has been a Postdoctoral Researcher with Ghent University and continues his work in propagation modeling. From October 2012 to September 2018, he was a Postdoctoral Fellow with FWO-V (Research Foundation—Flanders), Brussels, Belgium. In October 2015, he became a part-time Professor of medical applications of electromagnetic fields in and around the human body.

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